

SOCIO-POLITICAL PROCESSES IN UZBEKISTAN ON THE EVE OF INDEPENDENCE

Andijan State University Faculty of History 4th Year student

Abdivahobova Sugdiyona

Annotation: This article will talk about the socio-political life of Uzbekistan at the end of the 80s of the 20th century, the tragedy of Fergana, the granting of the status of the state language to the Uzbek language and the establishment of The Independent Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: Reconstruction, socio-political life, the tragedy of Fergana, the "Declaration of Independence"

Socio-political life in Uzbekistan at the end of the 80s of the XX century. It is known that in the 70-80s of the 20th century, the Sura of development of the economy in the USSR steadily decreased and its spending increased. Programs in social, food, agrarian, Energy, Ecology and other areas developed without taking into account the available opportunities did not work, deepening economic conflicts. Fergana tragedy. Reconstruction was also reflected in the escalation of interethnic relations. Problems in the socio-economic, political, cultural sphere, accumulated and formed for many years, could not but affect interethnic relations.

In May-June 1989, interethnic conflicts took place in Fergana, Tashkent regions and Andijan city, which caused a huge stir in the Republic and throughout the country, and led to a sharp turn of the political situation in the Republic. It is known that among a number of peoples deported by the mustabid regime during the Second World War were the Meskheti Turks, who were mainly settled in the densely populated region of Fergana, part in the regions of Andijan, Namangan and Tashkent, as a result of which there were additional problems in socio-economic and interethnic relations. This problem was ignored by the Sovet state

in time. On the contrary, by the time of" developed socialism "in the USSR," the national issue was completely resolved". A conflict arose between local youth and Meskheti Turks, and this conflict became public in the Fergana Valley. The political leadership of the Republic could not adequately assess this complex situation that had arisen. As a result, a simple conflict caused mass performances of residents, especially young people, interethnic clashes in Fergana, Margilon, Toshlok, Kokand, Andijan, Namangan, Tashkent.

The situation was further aggravated by the fact that the tragedy of Fergana was not properly reported in the Republican Press and other media, and the unilateral and nonlinear assessment that the "local population is to blame" for the origin of these conflicts. On June 11, about 100 of the Fergana youth working and studying in the city of Tashkent organized a demonstration on "Red Square", expressed an opinion against "incorrect" information about the events of Fergana, and made a number of other demands. Not "accustomed" to such public performances, to go against the order of communist ideology, the political leadership of the Muslim regime threw a military unit against the protesters. On June 8, 1989, peaceful protesters in Kokand were fired upon by soldiers of the same military unit, which resulted in the death of more than 50 residents who participated in the demonstration (many of whom were young people), and more than 200 wounded. A total of 103 people were killed, 1,009 injured, and 650 households were set ablaze and destroyed by interethnic clashes in the Fergana region between 3 and 12 June and their being fired upon by the military.

An analysis of information relating to the tragedies of Fergana shows that for the Meskheti Turks, this conflict was necessary as an excuse for them to return to their motherland, which was forcibly abandoned during the war on the fault of the Muslim system. The local population naturally assimilated into the conflict. Due to the large scale and tragic turn of events, Soviet and administrative authorities will hastily move the Meskheti Turks to a camp at the military unit site in Fergana

and to the Novgarzon settlement in the Asht District of the Leninabad region of Tajikistan. Thousands of people could not be kept long in such camps. Therefore, 16,282 people were transferred from the Fergana region to the Russian regions of Smolensk, orlovsk, Kursk, Belgorod and Voronezh.

The political dispute organized in Fergana was one of the dispute established in Tbilisi, Nagorno-Karabakh, Baku. There were later similar attempts at Boka and Parkent in February-March 1990, Osh and Özgan in June 1990. The evil forces did not achieve their goal. As a result of measures taken by the new leadership of Uzbekistan, the tension was overcome. By the 90s of the 20th century, changes in the world and former Union and the situation that arose accelerated the struggle of the Uzbek people for independence. In this place, the plenum of the Central Committee of the compartmentalization of Uzbekistan on June 23, 1989 and the election of Islam Karimov as the first secretary in it were of great importance. At this convention I. Karimov clearly defined the role and role of Uzbekistan in the former Union, proved that the restoration of cultural heritage and the reality of history, the development of national traditions and traditions is an objective necessity.

Uzbek is the state language. The issue of granting the status of the state language to the Uzbek language had already been raised by the Republican public. The former Uzbek leadership had previously viewed the issue as nationalistic, localist, and later attempted to elevate Uzbek and Russian to equal status, thus trying to pass a bill on bilingualism. The new head of the Republic took into account public opinion, chose a way to resolve the issue with pressure.

At the XI session of the Supreme Soviet of the Uzbek SSR on October 21, 1989, the law "on the state language of the Uzbek SSR" was adopted. The law established that the state language of Uzbekistan is Uzbek, the Uzbek language is fully valid in all spheres of political and social, economic and cultural life of the Republic. On February 19, 1990, the state program for the implementation of the

law"on the state language of the Uzbek SSR" was adopted. According to the law and state program, work in labor teams, educational institutions, enterprises and state institutions began to be transferred from Russian to Uzbek. The passage of this law and the beginning of its implementation was a major historical event in the social life of the Republic, another important step towards independence.

At the same time, conditions were to be created for the study of the Russian language and the languages of other peoples living in the Republic, the discretion of learning the language and the right to choose it were established by law. The passage of this law was of great importance for the Uzbek people, for the growth of the national self-awareness of the same people, for the preservation of interethnic harmony in the Republic. With the passage of the law on the language of the state, the realization of the national identity, another important political step of historical importance was taken in the Republic on the path to the restoration of national statehood.

On February 18, 1990, there was an election to the Supreme Soviet of Uzbekistan. The novelty of these elections was that alternative candidates were nominated in 326 of the 500 constituencies. In the previous elections, where all candidates were elected with almost 100 percent of the vote in the first round, this time in the first round, 368 candidates were able to collect the necessary votes. Re-elections were held in the remaining 132 counties. On March 23, 1990, the plenum of the Central Committee of the compartmentalization of Uzbekistan addressed the issue of the Republican political system. It emphasized that the transition of power in Uzbekistan to the form of Presidential rule is essentially a new stage in the sovereignty and statehood of the Republic.

On March 24, 1990, the 1st session of the Supreme Soviet of the Uzbek SSR of the XII convocation adopted the first political document within the framework of the USSR-"on the establishment of Presidential rule in Uzbekistan", and the first secretary of the Uzbek Compartmentary MK Islam Abduganievich Karimov

was elected president of the Uzbek SSR. Thus, Uzbekistan became the first within the republics of the USSR to establish a solid foundation for its national legal and Democratic state. Declaration of independence. One of the next important steps taken in Uzbekistan's independence was the adoption of the "Declaration of independence" by the Supreme Soviet of the Republic on June 20, 1990. The declaration proclaimed the state sovereignty of the Uzbek SSR based on the rules of international law, universal values and principles of democracy, based on the right of each nation to self-determination.

The declaration of independence consists of 12 articles, this document ensured the priority of the laws of Uzbekistan from the laws of the Union. At the same time, the " Declaration of Independence " ensured the management, legal activities of Uzbekistan, which existed until August 31, 1991, made it possible to conduct independent policies in all areas. The declaration proclaimed the state sovereignty of the Uzbek SSR based on the rules of international law, universal values and principles of democracy, based on the right of each nation to self-determination. With the adoption of the declaration, issues related to the economic and political life of the Republic in Uzbekistan began to be resolved independently.

In the Republic, the program " employment " was developed. According to this program, 300,000 people, mostly young people, were employed in 1990. In order to socially protect the low-income part of the population, in 1990, 142 million was raised from the budget and from the enterprise. the sum was further allocated. By 1991, bold work began to be done in Uzbekistan on the preparation and adoption of completely new state symbols on the state independence of the Republic. On February 15, 1991, the Supreme Council of Uzbekistan adopted a special resolution "on the state symbols of Uzbekistan".

The struggle of Uzbekistan for its sovereignty began to be distinguished, first of all, by the fact that each law adopted in the Republic was fundamentally

different in content and essence from the laws of the former Union, in addition, each law was not adapted to the law of the Union as before, but expressed the interests of the Republic. In particular, on July 22, 1991, the decree of the Presidium of the Supreme Council of the Uzbek SSR on the "transfer of state enterprises, institutions and organizations subordinate to the Union located on the territory of the Uzbek SSR to the legal subordination of the Uzbek SSR" was adopted by the president of the Uzbek SSR I.A. Karimov, the Supreme Council of the Uzbek SSR and the government are proof of the political and economic independence of Uzbekistan, the bold steps taken for its national sovereignty.

Literature:

1. Р. Абдуллаев, Қ.Ражабов, М.Раҳимов - Ўзбекистон тарихи (1917-1991 йиллар). 2 том - Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 2019
2. <https://arxiv.uz>
3. <https://fayllar.org>